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Deliverable D7.8

Report on Tutor-web training activities in FarFish

08/11/2021

Executive Summary

Training and capacity building are important components of the FarFish project, and one of the project's products are e-learning courses that are intended to educate stakeholders and scientist in the basics of fisheries management and stock assessment. The courses are made available at www.tutor-web.net. This report provides an overview of the e-learning component of the project, the tutor-web tool and the training activities facilitated by FarFish to promote uptake and use of the tool. The setup and content of the FarFish material available on Tutor-web has previously been reported on in previous FarFish reports but is briefly reviewed in the report to provide insight into why this platform is important and relevant for the FarFish project.

The Tutor-web training activities as originally planned included an in-country demonstration giving short local courses in the FarFish case study countries on the use of the tool, leaving expertise on how to teach fisheries management and stock assessments using personalized educational technology. The training activities were intended to constitute a proof of concept where the FarFish experts would travel on-site to the Seychelles to demonstrate the applicability of the solution. This plan was however disrupted by Covid 19, as travel to the Seychelles (or any of the other case study countries) by the European experts was considered irresponsible and unsafe. The proof of concept was as results incorporated into the UNESCO-GRO Fisheries Training Programme, where 28 fellows from 17 countries (including representatives from all of the FarFish case studies) attended. The training demonstrated the relevance of the FarFish Tutor-web component, where the students can learn about the basics of fisheries management and stock assessment with the e-learning materials. The training activity also provided indications that the platform would be used by the fellows to become the teachers and advocates of the Tutor-web platform when returning home.

The Tutor-web task within FarFish has in addition delivered three peer-reviewed journal articles, which are briefly discussed in this report.

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1 Introduction

Training and capacity building are important components of the FarFish project. Among the training and capacity building tools developed in the project are e-learning courses that are made available at www.tutor-web.net. This document reports on the training activities facilitated by FarFish to promote uptake and use of the tool. The setup [1] and content [2] of the FarFish material available on Tutor-web has previously been reported on, but is briefly reviewed in the report to provide insight into why this platform is important and relevant for the FarFish project.

The Tutor-web training activities as originally planned included an in-country demonstration giving short local courses in the FarFish case study countries, on the use of the system, leaving expertise on how to teach fisheries management and stock assessments using personalized educational technology. The training activities were intended to constitute a proof of concept where the FarFish experts would travel on-site to the Seychelles to demonstrate the applicability of the solution. This plan was however disrupted by Covid 19, as travel to the Seychelles (or any of the other case study countries) by the European experts was considered unsafe. The proof of concept was as results incorporated into the UNESCO-GRO Fisheries Training Programme, where 28 fellows from 17 countries (including representatives from all of the FarFish case studies) attended. The training demonstrated the relevance of the FarFish Tutor-web component, where the students can learn about the basics of fisheries management and stock assessment with the e-learning materials. The training activity also provided indications that the platform would be used by the fellows to become the teachers and advocates of the Tutor-web platform when returning home.

The Tutor-web task within FarFish has in addition delivered three peer-reviewed journal articles, which are briefly discussed in this report.

¹ Tutor-web FarFish initial setup <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3075477>

² FarFish Tutor-Web educational material <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4564862>

2 Tutor-web and the FarFish component setup

The tutor-web system (Stefansson, 2004) has been developed to be a mobile-web system as described by Lentin *et al.* (2014). Within the tutor-web, courses consist of tutorials, which contain lectures. The hierarchy typically contains both material and drills on said material. The system has been used for teaching and educational research and has been demonstrated to enhance learning over and above general classroom instruction (Jonsdottir, 2017). The system has been developed and enhanced so as to function in locations with unstable electricity and no Internet connection, both in remote areas (Stefansson, 2017) and even in isolated prisons (Njurai, 2017). The system uses a collection of methods to enhance student learning, from personalised drills through cryptocurrency rewards (Lentin and Stefansson, 2018).

During the preparation and early stages of the FarFish project, the consortium members interviewed stakeholders and potential target users of the FarFish Tutor-web tool, with the intent to identify their needs for e-learning materials related to the FarFish priorities, and how to best facilitate their capacity building requirements. The need for access to training materials in fishery science was highlighted, and it became clear from the discussions that there is a serious need not only for training in the use and applications of fisheries models, but also in the underlying mathematics, statistics and use of computers for analysis. For this reason, a fairly wide-ranging training and capacity building plan was setup, specially developed for FarFish users.

The setup was tailored to the Tutor-web platform and the material included updates of previously existing tutor-web courses that have been tailored for FarFish, as well as new teaching materials directed at FarFish target audience. The new material was made available in the tutor-web under the heading "Methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries." It consists of multiple tutorials, providing material and drills at various stages of development, on topics from prerequisite mathematics, statistics and programming, through introductory fish population dynamics to methods for data-limited fisheries.

3 FarFish Tutor-web educational materials

The educational materials added to Tutor-web by FarFish are related to methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries. The tutorials are broken into eight courses as shown in Figure 1.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a course. At the top, there is a green navigation bar with tabs for 'Contents', 'View', 'Edit', and 'Sharing'. To the right of the tabs are 'Actions', 'Display', and 'State: Published'. Below the navigation bar, the course title 'Methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries' is displayed in a large, bold font. Underneath the title, it says 'by admin — last modified Sep 03, 2021 09:34 AM — History'. A section titled 'Course tutorials' follows, with the text 'All tutorials this course contains'. Below this, there is a list of eight tutorial titles, each with a blue underlined link: 'A1: From numbers through algebra to calculus and linear algebra', 'A2: Overview of introductory statistics', 'A3: Applied multiple linear regression', 'B1: Introduction to fish population dynamics', 'B2: Modelling length at age and length distributions', 'B3: Statistical stock assessment methods', 'C1: Principles of utilization: The precautionary approach', and 'D1: Methods and applications for data-limited fisheries'.

Figure 1: A total of eight Tutor-web courses were produced/advanced within FarFish

Within each course there are series of lectures and associated drills (multiple choice questions) as the student is lead through the course with series of presentations and drills to make sure he understands the material. Figure 2 shows an overview of one of the courses.

Contents View Edit Sharing Actions Display Add new... State: Published

B2: Modelling length at age and length distributions (fish5103growth)

by Eva Dogg Steingrimsdottir — last modified Sep 02, 2021 10:03 PM — [History](#)

Take a drill on Lack of age data - background Download tutorial notes

Lectures Literature Related courses Data files

- Show raw tutorial TeX
- Update tutorial PDF

Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture10	Lack of age data - background	Download PDF	4	7
lecture20	Growth models	Download PDF	6	1
lecture30	Models of length distributions	Download PDF	13	6
lecture40	Case studies in analysis of length data	Download PDF	4	10
lecture50	Length-weight relationships	Download PDF	1	0
lecture60	Modelling the development of a length distribution	Download PDF	7	7
lecture70	Using length data in population models	Download PDF	2	1
lecture80	Using length data in population models	Download PDF	1	0

Figure 2: The course on “Modelling length at age and length distributions” consists of 8 lectures and 38 questions

A total of 200 new, FarFish related, drills were generated and added to the courses, which included basic issues such as what models are appropriate and what can potentially be estimated within data-poor scenarios.

The advantage of this tutor-web e-learning platform for FarFish is that students and stakeholders can select what lectures or tutorials they are interested, and progress as they feel comfortable with. They can if needed start with basic background statistics courses or jump right into the modelling and stock assessment courses.

The training demonstrated the relevance of the FarFish Tutor-web component, where the students can learn about the basics of fisheries management and stock assessment with the e-learning materials. The training activity also provided indications that the platform would be used by the fellows to become the teachers and advocates of the Tutor-web platform when returning home.

5 Publications

The Tutor-web task within FarFish delivered three peer-reviewed journal articles, which are available open access. The papers are as follows:

Stefansson G. and Jonsdottir A.H. (2021). Learning and evaluation without access to schools during Covid-19. INTED2021 Proceedings. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21125/inted.2021.0563>

- The paper discusses how innovative redesign was needed during COVID-19 in spring, 2020, to facilitate uptake and use of tutor-web education in Kenya.

Stefansson G., Jonsdottir A.H., Jonmundsson T., Sigurdsson G.S., Bergsdottir I.L. (2021). Identifying rote learning and the supporting effects of hints in drills. INTED2021 Proceedings. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21125/inted.2021.0556>

- The paper examines the difference between meaningful learning with emphasis on understanding of the thought material, and memorisation through repetition, within the context of Tutor-web.

Jonsdottir A.H., Jonmundsson T., Armann I.H., Gunnarsdottir B.B., Stefansson G. (2021). The effect of the number of distractors and the “none of the above” – “all of the above” options in multiple choice questions. INTED2021 Proceedings. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21125/inted.2021.1540>

- The paper examines how the probability of answering a question correctly within Tutor-web decreases with the number of distractors, such as NOTA and AOTA.

6 Conclusions and discussions

As part of FarFish, a course has been developed and set up on www.tutor-web.net in accordance with the objectives of the project. The outline consists of tutorials required for a course on fish population dynamics and utilisation in an ecosystem context in the case of data-limited fisheries. The tutorials contain lectures, which in turn contain drills designed to give students mastery of the prerequisites for assessments for data-limited stocks.

The tutor-web learning management system has been enhanced far beyond other such systems in that it allows an instructor to set up drills specific to class' data and even for each individual student to upload their own data to be used in the drills. The student group can also be asked to write examples and reports which other students are asked to peer-review through grades and feedback. The submitter can subsequently revise the submission and submit for a new review. These options are particularly relevant within the context of FarFish, where self-learning is facilitated using the e-learning platform.

The original plan was to demonstrate, test, validate and improve the Tutor-web content in a “proof of concept” in-country demonstration. This was however not possible due to Covid-19 and as plan B the demonstration was done among the students of the UNESCO-GRO-FTP, which come from 17 countries all across the world, including from each of the FarFish case study countries. The “proof of concept” worked fairly well, as it was demonstrated that the students/fellows appreciated the content and the platform and believed it would be useful for them when returning back to their home. Even thinking that they could use the platform to become teachers within their institutions.

The training activities did not materialise as originally planned, but the FarFish task leaders believe that the Tutor-web task delivered what was aimed for and the it will serve as an important e-learning tool into the future.

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[twstats] <https://github.com/tutor-web/twstats>

[HODF Templates] <https://github.com/shuttlethread/hodf/blob/master/README.md#templates>

